

GRADUATES' VIEWS ON THE EMPLOYMENT AFTER THE SARS EPIDEMIC: AN ANALYSIS

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ABSTRACT

The COVID-19 epidemic has had a significant impact on the world for about a year and a half. The global economy and other service industries have felt significant effects. It is the educational system that suffers the most during a pandemic, especially in a developing country like India that has not yet built the necessary infrastructure. Despite these obstacles, both students and educators have made preparations for online learning a priority. For exam scheduling specifically, this system leaves little room for error. Students' knowledge has been assessed in an entirely objective manner for nearly three semesters now through online examinations. We rarely test for the ability to reason and analyse. There are major flaws in the online exam system, including the potential for cheating and a lack of openness. Students are using dishonest practises. Given the current state of affairs, many bright young people have legitimate concerns about their prospects in the labour market as a result of the unfair competition they will encounter. This paper assesses how students feel about the employment market after COVID-19.

Keywords: *Issues of public opinion, the labour market, fierce rivalry, distance learning, SARS Epidemic*

INTRODUCTION

Both the economy and the educational system have suffered as a result of the COVID-19 pandemic. The widespread locking down has resulted in a shift from traditional classrooms to online learning. The COVID-19 epidemic has altered conventional modes of instruction and learning. Contrary to popular belief, there are actually quite a few drawbacks to the current educational system. Students benefited from being exposed to internet and technology, and they were able to continue their education even when their physical location was inaccessible due to a lockdown. However, there are many drawbacks to learning via the Internet. Only multiple-choice questions are included in the online exam format, which is insufficient. Thus, students' real-world expertise cannot be evaluated. When exams are given online, pupils have the opportunity to cheat. Some students frequently avoid the online lecture. And the student would have a hard time getting hired with grades like those.

Both the instructor and the student will require a high-speed internet connection in order to participate in online classes. The teacher will provide a link to a mobile app with the class, and

each student should already have a copy of the app installed on their own device. When students click the offered link, they are prompted to provide their login credentials in order to access the online lectures. However, this assumes access to high-quality devices and reliable internet, both of which may be more common in densely populated areas than in rural ones.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

To examine students' views on the post-pandemic job market

HYPOTHESIS OF THE STUDY

H1- It is the opinion of the students that the current educational system will have a detrimental impact on the future employment market in India.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The researcher has conducted a survey to learn about students' perspectives for the study's purposes and to achieve the study's objectives. A total of 286 undergraduates from disciplines as diverse as the arts, business, sciences, and engineering participated. A Google form was made available for them to fill out and submit their grades. The graduation year of these pupils was used to choose them. Those who will graduate in 2020 or 2021 and have passed their final exams. This was done with the intention of analysing how COVID affected their outlook on the labour market. Tabular data was used for analysis, and conclusions were formed from there.

ONLINE SCHOOLS' BENEFITS

Due to the Pandemic, Home Study is Now Possible. In order to participate in the online lecture, students will require access to the internet on a device. By allowing students to attend classes from the comfort of their own homes, parents are better able to monitor their child's academic progress than was previously possible.

Students now have more time to focus on extracurricular activities because to the time they've freed up from their online coursework. As a result of the shutdown, there are now numerous online classes that students can participate in. Students have also participated and benefited from this.

Many students who are working and going to school at the same time won't be able to physically attend their classes at the university. But it doesn't matter where you are because online classes may be accessed from any device. This student was afforded several opportunities to participate in classes and acquire education while having to balance their time between job and other commitments. There are a lot of people who will profit, including students who previously had to travel a long distance to attend university. Online lectures are becoming increasingly popular as students find them more convenient than making daily commutes to campus.

CONSIDERATIONS OF ONLINE LEARNING

When giving an online lecture, instructors are unable to engage in direct interpersonal communication with their students. It's not always clear to educators whether or not their class is present and paying attention. It's possible for students to multitask during an online class by playing a game on their phone and setting it aside during the presentation. In the past, teachers' ability to tell if a student had understood a concept was based on the student's reaction to the concept being presented.

One difference between online and traditional college lectures is that fewer people attend the former. In my experience, students rarely make it through more than one or two lectures before giving up and moving on to something else. Participation in online courses began strongly but has steadily declined over time. Many students are also seen playing games or watching TV while listening to their online class.

The lockdown due to the pandemic began in March 2020, right as the school year 2019-20 was winding down and final exams for all of the different schools and universities were still to be taken. There has been a trend in recent years for schools to award pupils with grades that are, on average, based on their previous achievement. Furthermore, in the new academic year 2020-21, the exam was given online, and students were given multiple-choice questions to answer. Pupils, along with their parents and educators, have voiced concern that this assessment method fails to adequately measure students' knowledge because it does not include testing of their ability to apply that knowledge in real-world contexts.

Since the exam is being given online, students from all around the world are taking the opportunity to cheat. They use a different phone to Google the answers, and many students even consult reference materials during tests. It has been observed that students with low percentages and average pupils are also scoring high percentages in these online exams. This exam format has been criticised by several pupils.

It will have an impact on students' ability to succeed in competitive tests and job interviews due to a lack of hands-on experience.

Lack of Access to Necessary Equipment/Technology: In order to see the online lectures and take the online exams, students require access to a computer or mobile device with a reliable internet connection. Many parents and students lack access to high-quality electronic equipment. This is a problem, as many kids do not have access to adequate internet. You can't afford to use the internet if you can't afford to eat. One of the most pressing issues was the fact that pupils in rural areas sometimes lacked the maturity to benefit from an education. Occasionally, it is seen that students who have access to the internet and gadgets nevertheless do not show up to lectures due to connectivity issues. Despite the fact that sometimes educators too lack adequate internet

access. Because of this, every month, the parents are now responsible for paying for the children's cell phones and internet service. This increased their regular outlay of money.

Unfortunately, the results that were announced during the online exam procedure were based on MCQs scores, not the students' actual performance. In other instances, the average performance was used to determine the result. It has been seen in many areas that students affected by the epidemic are not being failed and are instead being promoted by means that would be unfair to them—namely, the use of a Grace Mark. Since many students are earning greater percentages, this kind of result will also impair students' ability to gain admission for the next academic year. As an added downside, they face an uncertain professional future.

Unfortunately, disciplines like arithmetic, accounting, IT, chemistry, etc. are not well-suited to online learning and instruction. The importance of face-to-face interaction with these topics demands that you be there. Learn how to produce a thorough final account and balance sheet in an online exam, as well as how to exhibit the final account and tally it online. There's no way every student couldn't get this, but neither is it a walk in the park. In order to fully grasp this concept, a student's physical presence in the classroom is required.

Migrants had an impact on schools as many families were forced to leave the city once the lockdown was declared in March 2020. The people began to return to their homes and villages. Their college funding was cut in half as a result. Some of them dropped out entirely, while others tried to continue their studies from rural areas but lacked access to online classrooms. In addition, those migrant students' families will be unable to afford the necessary technology and internet access to enable them to attend school or pay for college because of financial hardships.

COVID-19 PANDEMIC'S ADVERSE IMPACT ON THE SCHOOLS

All aspects of life, including schooling, were badly impacted by covid-19. Changes have been made to both the study and examination schedules. The number of students enrolling in K-12 and higher education institutions has dropped noticeably as a result of the migration crisis. It is imperative that many schools lower their tuition rates. As a result, numerous schools have dismissed their teaching staff, leaving them unemployed. The population's disposable income has dropped due to the pandemic. They can't afford the costs associated with the extracurricular activities and coaching lessons. This impacted the workforce, particularly those involved in tutoring and the instruction of other extracurricular activities.

Since the past two school years have been under lockdown, years like grade 10, grade 12, and the final year of college and graduate school have lost much of their significance. Students have been studying all year, and it has been made clear that their final grade will be based on a weighted average or an exam consisting of multiple choice questions will be administered.

Students are less motivated to study since they know they will get good grades regardless of how hard they work. Knowledge gained in high school, especially the 11th and 12th grades, provides a crucial foundation for success in higher education. Students who do poorly or ignore their schoolwork this year are setting themselves up for failure in subsequent years because their foundation will be shaky.

The admissions procedure and the school year were both shortened as a direct result of the delays in receiving test results. In many cases, schools have cut back without informing students, who have suffered as a result. Students have not been adequately exposed to practical information during the past two years, and they have not been tested on this crucial area of knowledge either.

Preschoolers are as impacted as university students. I don't see how it's reasonable to assume that a young child, say in grades 1 through 8, will be able to sit through a four- to five-hour online course without getting bored or losing focus. The teacher can only view a small fraction of the class at any given time, so it's unclear how she'd be able to monitor their progress and behaviour in a virtual classroom. As a result, the covid-19 lockdown has had devastating effects on the academic community..

VIEWS ON THE JOB MARKET IN LIGHT OF THE COVID PANDEMIC

There have been disruptions in commerce and business administration due to the CoV-19 epidemic. The economic impact of the epidemic has been felt. The pandemic caused employment losses for even the most competent workers. Due to lockdown and losses during the epidemic time, organisations are unable to pay these payments and salaries to their employees and workers. We were dealing with the aftermath of the CoVD19 epidemic, although finding work had been difficult even before the outbreak. It was difficult for anyone, no matter how impressive their resume or how many years of experience they may boast, to land a high-paying job in the modern economy. It was a difficult job market for recent grads and post-grads. A number of engineering graduates were already struggling to find work prior to the pandemic, and the epidemic only made matters worse.

To get hired, education is crucial. Possessing strong practical experience is just as important as having a degree. Someone with an M.com, for instance, may not be able to add up the books, and any degree earned during this lockdown test phase may have been for show only. A substantial amount of practical experience is still necessary to keep one's employment, even if a degree gets you in the door.

Due to the epidemic, more and more schools are moving their courses online, where students lack access to hands-on training. This abstract idea is being taught only through virtual classrooms. Subjects like accounting and mathematics are notoriously challenging to teach via

video conference. Although classroom instruction is available on the topic, students have difficulty grasping it, and their questions remain unanswered. Students are not complaining about this kind of education, however, because their exams will likewise be given online and will consist solely of multiple-choice questions for which they need simply select the correct response from a list of options. Some students are getting very good grades in an online exam by copying from other students.

It's true that this method of education can lead to high grades and successful work, but at the expense of the practical experience employers increasingly value. Both kids and their parents were concerned because they anticipated a more competitive employment market. A high score on the CoVD19Pandemic is not recognised in the job market. Those who graduate or enrol in school during the Covington 19 pandemic face an uncertain future.

After hearing the interviewer say, "This is lockdown exam result we are not considering this as a valid," a number of students have conceded that the result was not taken into account. One more issue is that the average student now scores at the same level as the intelligent student, alongside those who were previously categorised as good and bad students, respectively. As a result, there would be no basis for continued admission or employment discrimination

DATA ANALYSIS

Sl. No.	Statement	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Total
1	Covid-19 pandemic has affected education sector negatively Percentage of Total	164	96	18	8	0	286
		57.34%	33.57%	6.29%	2.80%	0.00%	100.00%
2	Covid-19 pandemic has brought new trends to the Education sector Percentage of Total	96	166	12	10	2	286
		33.57%	58.04%	4.20%	3.50%	0.70%	100.00%
3	Covid-19 pandemic has created huge openings in the job market. Percentage of Total	44	92	38	90	22	286
		15.38%	32.17%	13.29%	31.47%	7.69%	100.00%
4	Online examination was relevant option during the Covid-19 period Percentage of Total	82	114	50	36	4	286
		28.67%	39.86%	17.48%	12.59%	1.40%	100.00%
5	The results of online examination genuinely depicted the skills/talents of the students Percentage of Total	38	140	70	12	6	286
		20.28%	48.95%	24.48%	4.20%	2.10%	100.00%

6	I am more comfortable in online education pattern than attaining the college every day. Percentage of Total	28	110	64	48	36	286
		9.79%	38.46%	22.38%	16.78%	12.59%	100.00%
7	I am able to focus on my studies in a better way rather than offline mode of education. Percentage of Total	36	114	68	42	26	286
		12.59%	39.86%	23.78%	14.69%	9.09%	100.00%
8	I am sure that job market will recruit potential candidates in the future course. Percentage of Total	66	116	64	34	6	286
		23.08%	40.56%	22.38%	11.89%	2.10%	100.00%
9	Covid-19 pandemic has increased the competition present in the job market. Percentage of Total	106	122	22	18	18	286
		37.06%	42.66%	7.69%	6.29%	6.29%	100.00%
10	The future of job market is not safe due to the degrees provided during the pandemic period Percentage of Total	92	140	34	16	4	286
		32.17%	48.95%	11.89%	5.59%	1.40%	100.00%
11	I am able to take up additional/vocational courses during the Covid-19 Pandemic period. Percentage of Total	78	104	32	56	16	286
		27.27%	36.36%	11.19%	19.58%	5.59%	100.00%

Source: From the primary data collected with the help of google forms

- The purpose of this study is to learn how students feel about taking exams and courses digitally. Primary data for this was gathered from 286 students across three disciplines: the sciences, business, and the arts.
- Seventy-three point three four percent of pupils strongly agreed, and thirty-three point five seven percent agreed, that the covivirus-19 pandemic has had an impact on the educational system.
- A majority of students (over 90%) believe that the CoVD19 epidemic has sparked a shift in the way schools operate.
- Nearly half (47%) of students agree that the pandemic has created new opportunities in the marketplace, while nearly 40% disagree (and the rest are agnostic).
- The results of a survey asking students whether or not taking an exam online during the flu outbreak showed that 28.67% strongly objected, 39.86% disapproved, 14% agreed, and the rest were neutral.

- Seventy percent of students were aware that these kind of tests do not accurately reflect their abilities, whereas 24.48 percent had no opinion either way.
- Nearly half (48%) of respondents indicated they are not at ease during online lectures and would rather attend a traditional college, while about a third (32%) expressed a preference for online education over traditional college and 22.38% were ambivalent.
- More over half of students stated they could concentrate better when not online and struggled to do so when studying online; almost a quarter of students indicated they could concentrate better when studying online than offline; 23.78 percent were neutral.
- Only 7% of respondents didn't think that the work market of the future is unstable, while 48.95% did.
- Of those polled, over 63.50 percent of students said they took advantage of the opportunity to attend elective or career-related courses during the covid-19 epidemic; 25 percent said no; the rest were unsure.

Scientific investigations have proven beyond a reasonable doubt that the current trend of evaluating and studying for courses entirely online is detrimental to students' academic development and professional prospects. The vast majority of pupils felt similarly. No amount of time spent on the internet can produce perfect mastery of every imaginable ability. Students will face increased competition and significant challenges as a result of this shift to online education.

CONCLUSION

Given the foregoing data, it's safe to say that recent grads are anxious about their prospects in the labour market. They feel discriminated against in both the job market and higher education arenas due to the current educational trend. The onus is now on state governments to research different ways of evaluating students' knowledge and abilities in the classroom. Going for face-off Vivas, where the educator can interrogate the student on his academic understanding and assess him based on this performance, is one possible alternative, especially during epidemic times. More opportunities like these should be made available so that people's skills and insights can be recognised. Job openings will be restricted to qualified individuals.

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